

TEACHING TECHNOLOGY OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSONS ON THE BASIS OF THE PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER

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Abstract. The article presents some ideas on the technology of teaching physical education lessons based on the innovative cluster of pedagogical education. One of the important aspects of the pedagogical skills of a physical education teacher is to arouse interest in students in completing tasks. The effectiveness of the physical education process largely depends on how it is carried out. On this basis, students are taught to analyze their actions and creatively search for ways to improve them. This is done either verbally or through self-analysis of the performed actions. The participants' way of thinking is important in mastering the movement technique being studied.

Keywords: Pedagogical education, innovative cluster, awareness and activity principle, Motivational actions, physical exercises, visual guidance.

Introduction. The main general methodological principles used in the educational process include a number of general rules of educational methodology. In the system of physical education education, there are also principles that determine the systematic structure in accordance with the content of education, which are divided into general social, general pedagogical, general methodological and special principles.

Adherence to the above principles is the starting point in determining the general methodology of the physical education process. Below we will dwell on some of them.

The principle of consciousness and activity. This principle is important in that it creates a strong relationship among students, stable interest, satisfaction of their needs for physical education and sports activities, and motivation for optimal performance. If the use of physical exercises is consistent, their systematic effect contributes to the successful development of the human body and psyche. The implementation of the principle under consideration is achieved through various exercise techniques, consciousness and an active attitude to the physical education process.

Consciousness is the ability of a person to correctly understand objective laws, to carry out his activities in accordance with them. The basis of consciousness is to predict the results of his activities in advance and clearly define realistic tasks. Reason provides information about the learning process,

helps in the formation of character, and also plays an important role in the development of individual, moral, psychological and professional qualities of a person. In the process of physical education, first of all, general exercises should help to form a conscious attitude to physical activity. Then students will have enough strength and a stable incentive to devote time to training, striving to mobilize all their strength over the years.

Literature analysis and methodology. A physical education teacher (coach) must work on strong motives and high goals that arouse a stable and healthy interest in the chosen direction or type of physical activity of students. Consciousness is important for the success of physical education. The type of activity that will be involved in the process of solving a problem related to the topic is determined by the teacher. When clearly stating each requirement, its meaning should be correctly conveyed to the participants.

One of the important aspects of the pedagogical skills of a physical education teacher is to arouse interest in students in completing tasks. The effectiveness of the physical education process largely depends on how it is carried out. On this basis, students are taught to analyze their actions and creatively search for ways to improve them. This is done either verbally or through self-analysis of the performed actions. The participants' way of thinking is important in mastering the movement technique being studied.

In the process of mastering and controlling stimulating actions, thinking creates the necessary conditions for improving motor functions. This is confirmed by numerous studies of the body's reactions to imaginary work. In training, a significant change is observed in comparison with the initial thinking process by performing tasks. In psychology, this is called ideomotor training.

Activity is a measure of the degree of action shown by a person, its application in practice. From a didactic point of view, activity serves as a necessary condition and result of the conscious assimilation of knowledge, skills and competencies. The views of such well-known psychologists as S.L. Rubinstein, L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leonov on the theory of activity note that human activity is a factor dependent on consciousness. At the same time, consciousness is the most important cognitive process in managing and regulating activity through knowledge, motivation, needs, interests and goals. This leads to the following requirements:

1. Setting the goals and objectives of the lesson, introducing the participants to them.

2. Conscious study and mastery of the elements of action in the pedagogical process.

3. Mastering the ways of applying the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in practice.

4. Forming a creative, active attitude to the process of initiative, independence and physical development.

Discussion and results. The use of special methodological methods in increasing alertness and activity has a special place. In observing and assessing students' movements, teaching self-control, the use of visual and auditory cues, repetition of the movements being studied (ideomotor training), and conversations on analyzing the technique are of particular importance.

Principle of clarity. The principle of clarity serves to widely use visual cues in the process of physical education. Visual cues are understood as the participation of human sensory organs in the process of cognition. Practical demonstration in the process of physical education is carried out in such forms as visual, audio, and motor. Visual cues (demonstration of general and internal movements, landmarks, visual cues, training videos) mainly help to clarify the spatial and spatio-temporal characteristics of movements.

Visual cues are also important in differentiating movements and developing sports and technical skills.

Sound guidance (in the form of various sound signals) is of primary importance in clarifying the temporal and rhythmic characteristics of movement elements. It significantly complements visual clarity. It should be noted that perception occurs through the visual system at three levels: through the sensory, expressive and auditory system. A person remembers 15% of the information received in the form of speech, and 25% in the form of visual. If these two methods of information transmission are used simultaneously, up to 65% of the information content is perceived.

Visual motor is inherent in physical education. Its importance is especially great in mastering the most complex movements, in guiding movement. The distinctive feature of visual motor is that it allows you to clarify movements in space and time, as well as control the existing dynamics.

The principle of individualization. requires taking into account the capabilities and characteristics of each person participating in physical education. This principle implies the selection and application of physical education tools and methods in accordance with the individual needs and abilities of each person. In the implementation of this requirement, the

fulfillment of one or another training load, the availability of tasks is determined. Readiness to perform tasks depends on the level of physical and intellectual development of the participants, their subjective attitude, expressed in their targeted behavior.

The purpose of the principle of individualization is to:

a) select optimal means, special conditions for the development of the abilities of each student;

b) eliminate overload, negative and harmful consequences.

The criteria for determining the available tasks are:

1) objective indicators - health-related, such as blood pressure, various functional tests, cardiograms; fitness-specific, such as the dynamics of sports results; dynamics of growth of physical qualities and technical training (productivity, maximum oxygen consumption, vital force - vital capacity of the lungs, etc.);

2) subjective indicators - sleep, appetite, full life, desire to exercise and participate in competitions, etc.

There are many factors by which physical education means and methods can be conditionally grouped. For example, the first group includes factors that characterize the general characteristics of the contingent of students (groups, teams). The second involves the combination of individual characteristics inherent in each student. The third group of factors arises in connection with the dynamics of general and individual changes in the process of physical education. The fourth group includes the tasks, methods and means of physical education.

The individual and general characteristics of participants are constantly changing. Physiological and psychological changes reflect the degree of presence of a particular task and requirement during one lesson.

The principle of continuity of the physical education process. The essence of the principle of continuity in physical education is based on the following rules:

1. The process of physical education is a holistic system that ensures consistency in the performance of physical exercises. The most important condition for the process of learning movements and developing physical qualities is consistency. The implementation of this rule in the process of physical education is determined by such didactic rules as "from easy to difficult", "from simple to complex", "from mastered to unmastered", "from knowledge to skills". Their effective implementation ensures the success of physical education in solving educational problems.

Physical exercises require a strict sequence of influence on the development of physical qualities. The development of each physical quality occurs as a result of functional and morphological changes in the body, as well as adaptability. This ensures consistency in imposing high demands on its functions. When organizing the educational process, it is necessary to base the determination of the sequence of development of means of movement and physical qualities on knowledge, taking into account the “transfer” of skills to positive and negative. When organizing the educational process, demonstrating the sequence of training means of movement and development of physical qualities requires material and technical support. The sequence of solving physical education problems during classes is characterized by the “traces” left after performing types of physical exercises. In particular, it is recommended to place speed exercises at the beginning of the lesson, and subsequent exercises are selected from the point of view of increasing endurance.

2. The principle of continuity is applied by physical education and sports specialists in organizing classes, preventing the interaction of classes, and long breaks. In teaching physical movements and developing physical qualities, classes must be interconnected. Only then will these effects be cumulative and the result will be effective. The effect of classes depends on the duration of the time interval separating each session. Therefore, breaks between classes should be optimal. In practice, it is well known that the effectiveness of teaching movements and developing physical qualities is low with long intervals between classes. The formed motor-coordination connections are very unstable and quickly disappear if they are not strengthened.

3. The principle of systematic alternation of loads and rest. In the process of physical education, it is important to regularly alternate loads and rest. This is due to the general effect of classes. Different options for rest between classes, the nature of the loads (intensity or direction) can lead to maximum results. To ensure that the body functions at different levels, repeated loads are necessary with strictly defined rest intervals. With long intervals between loads, adaptation to training occurs, with long rest intervals between loads. With short rest intervals, the body does not have enough time to restore its functioning. Regular repetition of loads against the background of reduced recovery leads to a decrease in the body's performance as a result of a decrease in resources. Initially, this occurs within physiological limits, and later, with overtraining and deeper pathological phenomena. The most optimal rest interval is the time

between loads necessary for the super-recovery phase (supercompensation) to occur.

The main feature of the principle of regular alternation of loads and rest in physical education is the organization of a process of alternating loads and rest in a certain system and order. The methodological methods used in the implementation of this principle are as follows:

- a) intelligent and purposeful repetition of tasks;
- b) changing and alternating loads and rest.
- c) repetition and variability of exercises and loads.

Conclusion. The principle of consistency affects physical development and physical education. In this case, it is necessary to systematically increase the requirements for the manifestation of the qualities of students involved in the movement. Incomplete rest - involves the subsequent performance of the work of students involved in the load against the background of significantly reduced recovery. Excessive tension, increased physiological loads lead to disruption of the normal functioning of the body. The dynamics of increasing physical activity should correspond to the nature of the heterochronicity, which is manifested in the adaptive reorganization of individual body systems.

There are also opposing tendencies, such as variability, in order to improve, maintain and ensure the stability of the achieved results. The skill of the teacher is the ability to correctly resolve this contradiction. Therefore, the principle of increasing and updating developmental and educational tasks in the direction of their complexity, the gradual increase in the volume and intensity of the load with the growth of the functional capabilities of the body, serves as a system.

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